

Diagnosis of Heart Disease using Fuzzy Logic

Rachana Mudholkar^{#1}, Harshada Chaudhari^{#2}, Mansi Kulkarni^{#3}, Yashshree Jangale^{#4},

Computer Engineering,

¹Dr. D. Y. Patil Institute of Engineering Management and Research, Pune, India

Abstract: Hospitals in both the developed and developing countries are faced with challenges in the treatment of patients with heart diseases; reasons being lack of adequate medical information. nutritional fluctuation, pressure and languor are among several factors that have led to development of Corazon issues to an extent of becoming fatal, making it a life threatening issue at an alarming rate. Though early prediction of cardiac illnesses is a noble thought since it assists in the identification of a civilization disease, efforts that have applied data capture to pinpoint delicate relations between symptoms and diseases are often suboptimal. Consequently, activities such as medical diagnosis, which are normally within the domain of subject-matter specialists, still present a difficult endeavor. The purpose of this research study is to create a fuzzy knowledge base expert system for recognizing patient status, with the goal of meeting this essential need. This system employs fuzzy rule base and membership functions to optimally categories the risk factors associated with the organization through use of fuzzy logic. It has the potential to revolutionizes the process of diagnosing the disease and offer dependencies to the healthcare professionals for timely and appropriate identification of the heart risks. The rationale for this suggested remedy is described by a called fuzzy logic a computing that imitates human thinking by tolerating vagueness and uncertainty. Fuzzy logic embraces the vagueness that is seen in diagnoses, unlike binary logic forms that just work in true or false paradigms. The fuzzy expert system would also provide an improved means of accommodating the intricacies of risk assessment of cardiac ailments by measuring the degree of membership of a particular variable to a specific fuzzy set and by applying the fuzzy rules for drawing conclusions based on the degrees in membership obtained. Thanks to the integration of logics of fuzzy's concepts the healthcare workers are able to use an effective tool for the early diagnosing of the patient with heart diseases. In this mode, there exists an opportunity for medical personnel to give personalized attention that is peculiar to every patient since risk factor assessment is integrated, while the procedure diagnosis is quite systematic. Conclusively, the implementation of fuzzy expert system is a notable step towards enhanced qualities of patient treatment and healthcare delivery system, reduction of the impacts of cardiac diseases on the patient and healthcare industry.

Keywords— Heart Disease, Fuzzy Logic, Diagnosis, Risk Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern society relies on computing technology for many applications, including diagnostic ones, and diagnosis is especially important when it comes to cardiologic diseases. Here diagnosis is not usually linked to the kind of technology used though the experts have to be proficient in the appropriate techniques and be very logical in their approach. Several methodologies like fuzzy logic, artificial neural networks, and genetic algorithms are incorporated into the system to help in diagnosing patients' conditions because medical data is often unpredictable. When it comes to the consideration of the means of handling the vagueness of data, one of the best methods is fuzzy logic. CVD still remains one of the major killers in the world, it is of paramount importance to diagnose these conditions as soon as possible in order to save as many lives as possible and minimize further harm. Given the many and diverse risk factors associated with heart disease and so many uncertainties in medicine, reaching a correct diagnosis of the condition may be difficult even with physicians of considerable experience. Hence, there are several reasons why early recognition of a heart attack is necessary if the goal is to do everything possible to minimize the amount of cardiac damage to the patient.

According to the World Health Organization, heart related diseases are now one of the largest killers globally, claiming millions of lives annually. In this work the type of data used was obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Repository database. The rest of this essay is organized as follows: In the next section, several researchers' works on the symptoms of heart diseases are compared before defining attributes of database design and their ranges in the following Section III. Finally, in Section IV, an understanding of the proposed approach is given; specifically, the focus is on the development of a fuzzy expert system. In section V, a summary of the system and the comparison of the results to prior studies is given. Section VI of this paper involves a recap of recommendations and research future avenues.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND OBJECTIVE

In the diagnosis of heart disease using fuzzy expert system, data mining techniques and many others, several papers that have been written are as follows Ali-Mehdi [1] used a fuzzy expert system of accuracy 94% . This paper employed data from the Virtual Assembly of Medical Applications (VAMA) data base from the V. A. Medical Center, Long Beach as well as Cleveland Clinic Foundation data base. For the implementation, they have used the MATLAB software and also used the input attributes of 13 and number of rules is forty-four. Baihaqi et al. [2] had done work on the identification of the used data mining techniques in quantitative value of 81. 82% accuracy. According to rule base, they have used C4. 5, CART and RIPPER. The One drawback of Adamos and Thomas' system is that it was actually implemented on 411 data sets. Paul et al.[3] developed fuzzy decision support system GPS using genetic algorithm to diagnose heart disease. In this paper, they have utilized FDSS based on the preprocessed datasets and the selected effective attributes generated from correlation coefficient with the help of required and by weighing the least squares method, (WLS). The Artificial Immune Recognition System and Fuzzy Weighted Pre-processing System was developed by Polat et al. in the year 2006[4] for diagnosis of heart disease with relative accuracy of percentage. In this paper, results of the system were displayed by using a confusion matrix. Uguz et al.[5] implemented a fuzzy discrete hidden model. In this paper, they have mentioned that the performance of the Surgeon integral based method is better than the performances of artificial neural network (ANN) and HMM based classification systems. In [6], Khatibi-Montazerac presented a hybrid interface engine to determine the risk level subsequently attaining ninety one percent simulation. 58 %. Proaicst spoke about their prediction model of the share of voice based on deterministic–probabilistic method of the Dempster-Shafer theory of evidence and the theory of fuzzy sets. Muthukaruppan [7] presented a paper titled 'Particle Swarm Optimization based Fuzzy Expert System for Heart disease' at International Conference on Energy, Communication, Data Analytics and Soft Computing (ICECDS-2017) 3183. They have taken proper input attributes by using decision tree to construct the DT because the dataset contain numerous attributes. In this paper, they have provided a clear and comprehensive attribute information with reference to their ranges and comments made on them. Tay and Gue [10] also used retarded Fuzzy Logic for the detection of heart disease and to minimize the distinguishing features Oad et al. [8] . They have used only 6 input attributes with member function declaration by considering them in a general manner. Sikchi-Sikchi [9] applied the FES in the MATLAB software. They have developed graphical user interface by using visual studio but the integration of MATLAB has also been made. Rathod-Gawande [10] employed a fuzzy expert system model for diagnosis with the highest accuracy level of 94%. Reacting to the fact that the initial input table contains 11 input attributes and 1 output attribute. This system applied the interface mechanism of mamdani. Sijimol et al.[11] proposed a FPN system to measure the risk level of heart disease calculation. They have collected the data of medical center with the help of database of V. A. and for analysis, they have considered 11 in put parameter among 76. Also, they have planned and computed the output for 0 to 4 parameters as well. Sudhakar Manimekalai [12] proposed a new approach in differentiating heart disease. They have used a unique methodology to find out the practicality of the risk factor and do this with the help of Fuzzy logic toolbox and SQL. In the current paper, defuzzification has been conducted using the centroid method. Kumar [13] uses an Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System for solving heart disease with accuracy of 92. Most of the inputs are presented with 00% while the author has only incorporated 13 input attributes and one output attribute. To facilitate diagnosis, Pathania-Ritika [15] designs a fuzzy controller. It means to differentiate the risk level; they employed 6 Input parameter and 1 output attribute. A survey paper on dengue fever was reviewed and recommended by Kasbe-Pippal [16]. They have described all the symptoms with knowledge of previous works on dengue and they have also introduced first dengue fever vaccine. Sayad Halkarnikar [17] proposed method, based on the use of neural network. In this paper, the system has been developed by using Multi-Layer Perception Neural Network (MLPNN) back propagated algorithm.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this section the fuzzy membership functions used, in the implementation part of the fuzzy expert system designing part, which includes the range for all the input attributes and the fuzzy rule base are demonstrated.

A. Fuzzy Membership Function

Trapezoidal Membership Function:

Definition Let $\mu(x)$ be a trapezoidal membership function which is characterized with four parameters 'a', 'b', 'c' and 'd' where 'a' and 'd' represent the lower and upper limit respectively but 'b' and 'c' represent limits on the vertical axis.

The trapezoidal membership function $\mu(x)$ is defined as:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq a \text{ or } x \geq d \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a} & \text{if } a < x < b \\ 1 & \text{if } b \leq x \leq c \\ \frac{d-x}{d-c} & \text{if } c < x < d \end{cases}$$

The length of the given trapezoid will be determined by four parameters designated as a, b, c, and d.

Triangular Membership Function:

Definition: There are three variables namely a, b, and c to characterize a triangular membership function where a and c are the limits of the triangular membership function and b is the point of inflection.

The triangular membership function $\mu(x)$ is defined as:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq a \text{ or } x \geq c \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a} & \text{if } a < x < b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b} & \text{if } b \leq x \leq c \end{cases}$$

Where a, b, and c are the parameters defining the triangular shape.

B. Design of Fuzzy Expert Systems:

An uncertainty problem is a fundamental use in a fuzzy expert system. Decisions and inference are the two key concepts in the development of a fuzzy expert system and defining the input and output variables dictate the former. This makes a total of ten input fields and one output field included in the system. The first field displayed in the output shows if the patient is a candidate for having heart disease [15].

- Age: This is a relative contraindication because patient age has no direct bearing on the process of LASIK eye surgery making it irrelevant for the purpose of a case against LASIK surgery.
- Blood Pressure: The measurements usually taken when it comes to blood pressure include diastolic and systolic blood pressure.
- Cholesterol: The cholesterol level, which is significantly present in the blood.
- Blood Sugar: The fasting blood glucose concentration, otherwise known as glycemia, is the level of glucose in the blood first thing in the morning, before eating.
- ECG: The civilizations of an electrocardiogram's readings as possessing distinct enhancements that benefit the characters.
- Max Heart Rate: The maximal rate of heart beating that could be achieved in case of stress

- appears to be such.
- Exercise: The amount of physically active time which refers to how many hours the patient spends on moderate or vigorous exercise every week.
 - Old Peak: The changes of ST level in exercise at the comparison to rest exercise-induced ST depression.
 - Thallium: Stress testing results shows that thallium is a resistant material to heat compression and tension.
 - Sex: The next relevant piece of information about the patient is the patient’s gender.
 - Chest Pain: Tidiness of chest pain is determined by complexity of chest pain and it has four levels namely no chest pain, mild chest pain, moderate chest pain and severe chest pain.

Variables entered: Tables 1 and 2 present the range values and membership functions of the variable in the inputtable below:

I. Table 1: Ranges Of Input Parameter

Input variables	Ranges	Fuzzy set values
Age	<29 29-38 38-58 52-100	Young Medium Old Very Old
sex	0 1	Male Female
Thallium	<=3 >=6 >7	Normal Medium High
Old peak	0-1 1.5-2.5 2.5-...	Low Risk Terrible
Exercise	1 0	True False
Max heart rate	0-100 100-152 152-...	Low Medium High
ECG	-0.5 -0.4 0.2 -1.8 1.4 -...	Normal Abnormal Hypertrophy
Blood Sugar	0-105 105-...	Normal High
Cholesterol	0-151 151-197 197-263 281-...	Low Medium High Very High
Blood Pressure	0-111 11-134 134-157 157 - ...	Low Medium High Very High
Chest Pain	1 1-2 2-3 3-4	Typical angina Atypical Anginal Non-anginal Pain Asymptomatic

Result parameters: The disease condition has been described as the output variable within the context of this study. This variable represents the state of the disease in relation to the value provided of the input and shows the condition from the perspective of the physician or other medical professional. It is an entire number that can be up to 5 or any number lower than that but not equal to zero. It is now necessary to define the base of fuzzy data rules that will be used in the process of decision making.

II. Table 2: Result Table

Output Field	Ranges	Fuzzy Set Value
Result	<1.78	Healthy
	1-2.51	Sick (s1)
	1.78-3.25	Sick (s2)
	1.5-4.5	Sick (s3)
	3.25>	Sick (s4)

C. Base of Fuzzy Data Rules:

Without any doubt, one of the most important parts of the said fuzzy interface system is the fuzzy rule base that in one way or another influences the final outcome of the developmental process. The set of several rules or a single rule that may include a single attribute or a combination of attributes through AND/OR operators is called a fuzzy rule base. In the implementation section, 54 rules are implemented in a manner consistent with the combination formula. That is why, in the rule basis, it is the whole variable with the correct output of the fuzzy set value used. For example, if patient is young and he/she has low blood pressure, it means he/she has sick1.

D. Fundamentals and Architecture of Fuzzy Logic:

Fuzzy logic is the mathematical way of generalizing the notion of two-valued logic, with further possibilities of the truth value ranging from 0 to 1 in order to handle with uncertainty and vagueness. The elements of fuzzy sets classification are used for the representation of the vague ideas, and the linguistic variables are applied for transferring of the qualitative information.

Fuzzy sets are sets whose elements lie in a range, and are described by membership functions whose outputs, for a given element, may range from 0 to 1.

Linguistic Variables: Instead of sharp numerical figures, calls for numbers or general words or terms which will include young, high, low, and so on are used to meet the variables.

Fuzzy Rules: Thus, in construction of the then-part of the ifthen rule, one usually needs to define the output membership function in terms of the input fuzzy sets.

III. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE SYSTEM

The fuzzy logic system is made up of various crucial parts. The fuzzy logic system is made up of various crucial parts: Fuzzification involved the use of appropriate membership functions to map the input crisp values onto fuzzy sets.

The part in a fuzzy-PID system responsible for using sets of fuzzy rules to arrive at the fuzzy output from fuzzy input values is referred to as the fuzzy inference engine.

Rule base: A set of fuzzy rules that contains the expert knowledge or experience that has been used in the process of mapping inputs to outputs.

Defuzzification is the process of converting fuzzy output values as the results of computational function to crisp values to help in decision making.

Fig.1. Architecture of the system

IV. RESULT

This work has been implemented with the following table values, which are taken from UCI machine database.

II. Table 3 : Input data

BP	SCHL	MHR	CP	FBS	OP	TScan	Sex	Age	ECG	CG	Results
130	256	142	3	1	0.6	6	1	56	2	1	2
132	224	173	3	0	3.2	7	1	58	2	0	2.77
160	164	245	4	1	6.2	7	0	62	2	0	3
110	239	142	4	0	1.2	7	1	59	2	1	2
128	175	122	1	0	0.4	3	1	32	0.4	0	1.2
110	239	126	4	0	0	7	1	54	0	0	2
140	293	170	4	0	2	7	1	60	2	1	2.03
108	243	152	3	0	0	3	1	47	0	0	1.4
135	304	170	3	1	0	3	0	54	0	0	0

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The fuzzy expert system that was created to diagnose heart disease shows encouraging outcomes; it outperforms earlier nonexpert techniques and achieves a high accuracy of 93.33%. This system mimics expert-doctor behavior through the use of fuzzy logic, membership functions, and a rule foundation, making it user-friendly for both doctors and patients. Moreover, its ability to adjust to ambiguous data points to possible uses outside the detection of cardiac disease. In the future, the model might be applied to other.

Health-related datasets and its rule base could be expanded for even greater accuracy. All things considered, this model offers a useful tool for precise cardiac disease diagnosis and prediction, with potential applications in other areas of medicine. In order to achieve a greater accuracy result, future research should test for other comparable systems or other data sets to evaluate its quality. To achieve greater accuracy in this suggested system, more new rule bases can be generated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are incredibly grateful to our project guide, Mrs. Rachana Mudholkar, for her ongoing input as well as her technical assistance, direction, moral support, and encouragement in seeing the project through to completion.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Adeli and M. Neshat, "A fuzzy expert system for heart disease diagnosis," in International Multi Conferences of Engineering and Computer Scientist (IMCECS2010), Hong Kong, pp. 1-6, 2010.
- [2] N. A. Setiawan, I. Ardiyanto, and W. M. Baihaqi, "Rule extraction for fuzzy expert system to diagnose coronary artery disease," in International Conference on Information Systems and Electrical Engineering (ICITISEE), Indonesia, pp. 136-141, 2016.
- [3] A. K. Paul, P. C. Shill, M. R. I. Rabin, and M. A. H. Akhand, "Genetic algorithm based fuzzy decision support system for the diagnosis of heart disease," in International Conference on Informatics, Electronics and Vision (ICIEV), Bangladesh, pp.145-150, 2016.
- [4] K. Polat, S. Güne, and S. Tosun, "Diagnosis of heart disease using artificial immune recognition system and fuzzy weighted pre-processing," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2186- 2193, 2006.
- [5] H. Uguz, A. Arslan, R. Sarac, and I. Turkoglu, "Detection of heart valve diseases by using fuzzy discrete hidden Markov model," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 2799–2811, 2008.
- [6] V. Khatibi and G. A. Montazerac, "A fuzzy- evidential hybrid inference engine for coronary heart disease risk assessment," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 37, no. 12, pp. 8536-8542, 2010.
- [7] S. Muthukaruppan, "A hybrid particle swarm optimization based fuzzy expert system for the diagnosis of coronary artery disease," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 39, no. 14, pp. 11657-11665, 2012.
- [8] X. DeZhi, P. K. Butt, and K. K. Oad, "A fuzzy rule based approach to predict risk level of heart disease," *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 17-22, 2014.
- [9] S. S. Sikchi and S. Sikchi, "Design of fuzzy expert system for diagnosis of cardiac diseases," *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 55-61, 2013.
- [10] A. B. Rathod and P. S. Gawande, "Design of rule based fuzzy expert system for diagnosis of cardiac diseases," in National Conference on Innovative Trends in Science and Engineering, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 313-320, 2016.
- [11] S. A. Sijimol, P. Vijayan, and S. Koshy, "Cardiovascular disease diagnosis using fuzzy petri net," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology (IJERT)*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 451-453, 2014.
- [12] K. Sudhakar and M. Manimekalai, "A novel methodology for diagnosing the heart disease using fuzzy database," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 84-89, 2015.
- [13] A. V. Senthil Kumar, "Diagnosis of heart disease using Advanced Fuzzy resolution Mechanism," *International Journal of Science and Applied Information Technology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 22-30, 2013.

- [14] O. Opeyemi and E. O. Justice, "Development of neuro-fuzzy system for early prediction of heart attack," *International Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science*, vol. 4, no. 9, pp. 22-28, 2012.
- [15] N. Pathania and Ritika, "Implementation of fuzzy controller for diagnose of patient heart disease," *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 694- 698, 2015.
- [16] T. Kasbe and R. S. Pippal, "Dengue Fever: State- of-the-Art Symptoms and Diagnosis," *International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 26–30, May 2016.
- [17] A. T. Sayad and P. P. Halkarnikar, "Diagnosis of heart disease using neural network approach," *International Journal of Advances in Science Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 88-92, 2014.
- [18] S. Kumar and G. J. Kaur, "Detection of heart diseases using fuzzy logic," *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 2694-2699, 2013.
- [19] S. S. Sikchi, S. Sikchi, and A. M. S., "Generic medical fuzzy expert system for diagnosis of cardiac diseases," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 66, no. 13, pp. 35-44, 2013.
- [20] UCI Machine Learning Repository: Heart Disease Data Set, Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Heart+Disease>